

Determination of clopidogrel by visible spectrophotometry in pure form and pharmaceutical formulations

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Abstract : Four simple and sensitive spectrophotometric methods (M_1 - M_4) for the determination of clopidogrel (CLO) are described. They are based on the charge transfer complex (C-T) formation between CLO and 2,3-dichloro-5,6-dicyano-1,4-benzoquinone (DDQ) (450 nm, method M_1), ion association complex formation between CLO and citric acid/acetic anhydride (560 nm, method M_2), oxidation followed by charge transfer complex formation between CLO and *N*-bromosuccinimide-metol (monomethyl-*p*-aminophenol hemisulfate)-sulphanilamide (SA) (520 nm, method M_3), oxidation-coupling between CLO and iron(III)-1,10-phenanthroline (510 nm, method M_4). The results obtained by each proposed method are compared statistically by means of Student's *t*-test and *F*-test with that of the reported method. They are found to be in good agreement. No interferences are observed from common pharmaceutical excipients. The proposed methods are selective, simple, accurate and economical for the quantitative determination of clopidogrel.

Keywords : Clopidogrel, 2,3-dichloro-5,6-dicyano-1,4-benzoquinone, *N*-bromosuccinimide-metol (monomethyl-*p*-aminophenol hemisulfate)-sulphanilamide, citric acid/acetic anhydride, iron(III)-1,10-phenanthroline.

Introduction

Clopidogrel (CLO), (+)-(*S*)-methyl 2-(2-chlorophenyl)-2-(6,7-dihydrothieno[3,2-*c*]pyridin-5(4*H*)-yl) acetate is an antiplatelet agent drug. It is official in US Pharmacopoeia method¹. Literature survey reveals that there are different types of assay methods for the determination of CLO in pharmaceutical dosage forms. These include simultaneous estimation of clopidogrel-bisulphate and aspirin by employing second derivative spectrophotometry², spectrophotometric and spectrodensitometric determination of alkaline degradation products of clopidogrel³, spectrophotometry^{4,5}, voltammetry⁶, kinetic spectrophotometry⁷, chromatography^{8,9}, HPLC¹⁰, UPLC¹¹; RP-HPLC method was achieved for the simultaneous estimation of aspirin and clopidogrel by octadodecylcolumn (C_{18})¹², RP-HPLC^{13,14}, HP-TLC¹⁵, visible spectrophotometric estimation of the drug by ion pair formation with Eriochrome Black T¹⁶, UV¹⁷, LC¹⁸, capillary electrophoresis¹⁹. Almost all these methods need expensive equipment, preventing their use in routine clinical laboratories. The authors made some attempts to develop some visible spectrophotometric methods by exploiting the basic nature of

the drug and succeeded in this direction. In the present paper four visible spectrophotometric methods and their application for routine as sulphanilamide of CLO in bulk form and tablets are described. These methods are based on the formation of colored charge transfer complex with 2,3-dichloro-5,6-dicyano-1,4-benzoquinone (method M_1), ion-association complex formation between CLO and citric acid/acetic anhydride (method M_2), oxidation followed by charge transfer complex formation between CLO and *N*-bromosuccinimide-metol/sulphanilamide (method M_3), oxidation-coupling between clopidogrel and iron(III)-1,10-phenanthroline (method M_4). All these methods are simple, rapid, and accurate, need neither special apparatus nor expensive reagents.

Results and discussion

Optimum operating conditions used in the procedures were established adopting variation of one variable at a time (OVAT) method. The optical characteristics such as Beer's law limits, molar absorptivities, regression equation and correlation coefficients obtained by linear least squares treatment of the results are given in Table 1. The

Table 1. Optical and regression characteristics, precision and accuracy of the proposed methods for clopidogrel

Parameter	DDQ (M ₁)	CA/AC ₂ O (M ₂)	NBS-Metol (M ₃)	Fe(1,10-phen) (M ₄)
λ (nm)	450	560	520	510
Beer's law limits ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	5–35	10–20	4–16	10–50
Detection limit ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	2.614×10^{-1}	2.494×10^{-1}	2.525×10^{-1}	1.734×10^{-1}
Sandle sensitivity	4.40×10^{-2}	5.71×10^{-2}	9.09×10^{-2}	2.10×10^{-2}
Molar absorption coefficient (ϵ)	7.3×10^3	5.7×10^3	8.85×10^3	1.53×10^4
Slope (b) ^a	0.02243	0.01755	0.02865	0.01099
Standard deviation of the slope (S_b)	1.356×10^{-4}	5.916×10^{-5}	1.907×10^{-4}	1.714×10^{-5}
Intercept (a) ^a	0.00215	-0.001	-0.004	0.3657
Standard deviation of the intercept (S_a)	1.786×10^{-3}	1.5175×10^{-3}	2.412×10^{-3}	6.335×10^{-4}
Standard deviation of estimation (S_c)	0.001775	0.001323	0.1897×10^{-2}	0.606×10^{-3}
Correlation coefficient	0.9999	0.9999	0.9999	0.9999
Relative standard deviation (%) ^b	1.34	1.15	1.6	0.34
% Range of error (confidence limit)				
$p = 0.05$ level	1.54	1.32	1.83	0.39
% Error in bulk samples	+0.05	-0.27	+0.12	-0.35

^aFor regression equation $y = a + bC$, where c is the concentration in mg/mL and y is absorbance.
^bSix replicate samples.

precision and accuracy were found by analysis of six separate samples containing known amount of the drug, and the results are summarized in Table 1. The relative standard derivation and % range of error at the 95% confidence level are also given in Table 1. These methods are applied for the determination of clopidogrel in tablets. These results obtained from the proposed and UV reference methods²⁰ are compared statistically by means of Student's t-test and by the variance ratio F-test, and no significant difference (Table 2) is observed. It indicates that none of the usual excipients like talc, starch employed in the formation of dosage forms interfere in the analysis of drug by the proposed methods. As an additional check of accuracy, recovery experiments were performed by the standard addition method. These results are also summarized in Table 2.

Chemistry of the colored species :

Method M₁ : DDQ forms a charge transfer complex with drugs containing basic nitrogen (the basic nitrogen as n-donor and DDQ as π -acceptor). The charge transfer complex dissociates into radical anions in highly polar solvents like dimethyl formamide and dioxane. Complete electron transfer from the donor to acceptor moiety takes place with the formation of intensely colored radical an-

ions. The structure of the charge-transfer complex formed with clopidogrel is shown in Scheme 1.

Method M₂ : It was noted in the literature²¹ that when distinctly basic tertiary amines are heated with a solution of citric acid (or *cis*-aconitic anhydride) in acetic anhydride, a red to violet color develops²². The color reaction²³ was reported to be selective for tertiary amines. In preparing the citric acid-acetic anhydride (C-A) reagent, citric acid is heated with acetic anhydride. The *trans*-configuration of aconitic acid initially forms through dehydration and subsequently yields α,γ -anhydroaconitic acid besides *cis*-aconitic anhydride; α,γ -anhydride develops violet color (and also fluorescence) in the presence of tertiary amines which allows the colorimetric and fluorimetric determination of that class of compounds. The colored (and fluorescent) compound forms between the tertiary amine and α,γ -anhydroaconitic acid. The tertiary amino group in clopidogrel permits the development of a new spectrophotometric method for its determination (Method M₂) is represented in Scheme-2.

Method M₃ : *N*-Bromosuccinimide acts as an oxidant and oxidizes clopidogrel. After the oxidation, the unreacted *N*-bromosuccinimide is colorimetrically determined with metol-sulphanilamide system²⁴. The reaction of the drug

Table 2. Assay of clopidogrel in pharmaceutical formulations

Formulation No. ^a	Labelled amount (mg)	Amount found (mg) using proposed methods				Found by reference method	% Recovery by proposed methods			
		M ₁	M ₂	M ₃	M ₄		M ₁	M ₂	M ₃	M ₄
1	80	Metol/NBS-SA	CA-AC ₂ O	Fe(1,10-phen)	DDQ	80 ± 0.72	100.1 ± 0.1	99.8 ± 0.2	99.8 ± 0.1	100.0 ± 0.2
		80 ± 0.58 F = 1.49 t = 0.37	80 ± 0.77 F = 1.17 t = 1.16	80 ± 0.77 F = 1.17 t = 1.16	80 ± 0.91 F = 1.6 t = 0.53					
2	80	80 ± 0.25 F = 2.16 t = 1.7	80 ± 0.17 F = 1.0 t = 1.98	80 ± 0.21 F = 1.52 t = 0.43	80 ± 0.21 F = 1.52 t = 1.58	80 ± 0.17	99.7 ± 0.2	100.1 ± 0.1	99.8 ± 0.1	100.1 ± 0.2
		40 ± 0.28 F = 2.41 t = 0.44	40 ± 0.28 F = 2.41 t = 1.77	40 ± 0.20 F = 1.23 t = 1.87	40 ± 0.25 F = 1.92 t = 1.68					
3	40	40 ± 0.53 F = 1.84 t = 0.23	40 ± 0.43 F = 1.21 t = 0.56	40 ± 0.31 F = 1.58 t = 1.56	40 ± 0.41 F = 1.1 t = 1.95	40 ± 0.18	100.2 ± 0.1	99.9 ± 0.2	100.0 ± 0.1	99.8 ± 0.2
		40 ± 0.53 F = 1.84 t = 0.23	40 ± 0.43 F = 1.21 t = 0.56	40 ± 0.31 F = 1.58 t = 1.56	40 ± 0.41 F = 1.1 t = 1.95					

^aDifference batches of tablets from four different pharmaceutical companies.
^bAverage ± standard deviation of six determinations, the t- and F-test values refer to comparison of the proposed method with reference method. Theoretical values at 95% confidence limit : F = 5.05, t = 2.57.
^cRecovery of 10 mg to the pre analyzed pharmaceutical formulations (average of three determinations).

Scheme 1. Structure of the charge-transfer complex formed with clopidogrel.

Scheme 2. The colored (and fluorescent) compound forms between the tertiary amine and α,γ -anhydroaconitic acid.

molecule with the PMBQMI formed *in situ* from metal and oxidising agent results in the formation of a colored product. The formation of charge-transfer complex in-

volving two moles of PMBQMI and one mole of sulphanilamide may be represented as π - π^* electron transfer and hydrogen-bond formation between quinone imine

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oxygen and amino hydrogen of sulphanilamide. The color species formation of the above method (M_3) is represented in Scheme 3.

Method M_4 : Acting as an oxidant, a ferric salt converts into a ferrous salt. They can easily be detected by the usual reagent for divalent iron, potassium ferricya-

nide²⁵, *o*-phenanthroline²⁶, bipyridyl or triazine²⁷.

o-Phenanthroline forms a complex of low tinctorial value with iron(III) which in turn functions as a better oxidant than Fe^{II} itself. The reduction product of tris-complex of iron(II) is known as ferroin. Based on its complexing ten-

Scheme 3. The formation of charge-transfer complex involving two moles of PMBQMI and one mole of sulphanilamide is represented.

dency and oxidizing properties, ferric salt was suggested in the estimation of several drugs. Clopidogrel exhibits reducing character and so is capable to reduce iron(III) to iron(II). In the present investigation, clopidogrel was treated with excess iron(III) salt under specified experimental conditions. Acting as an oxidant, iron(III) reduces to iron(II). This corresponds to the drug concentration. It can be estimated by the usual reagent for divalent iron, *o*-phenanthroline or 2,2'-bipyridyl. Experiments showed that *o*-phenanthroline is more sensitive reagent to estimate iron(II) in the reaction medium rather than the second one. So the estimation of iron(II) was carried out with *o*-phenanthroline in this method (M_4). The formation of colored complex (well known as Ferrioin) in this method is due to the involvement of iron(II) (formed through the oxidation of clopidogrel) and *o*-phenanthroline. The structure of this complex is shown in Scheme 4.

methods are simple, sensitive and useful for the determination of clopidogrel in pure samples and pharmaceutical formulations.

Experimental

Instruments :

A Systronic model 106 visible and Milton roy spectronic 1201 UV-Vis spectrophotometers were used for absorbance measurement. An Elico LI-120 digital pH meter was used for pH measurement.

Reagents :

All the chemicals are of analytical grade. 2,3-Dichloro-5,6-dicyano-1,4-benzoquinone (DDQ) (0.1% or $4.40 \times 10^{-3} M$) in dioxane for method M_1 , citric acid (3% or $0.72 \times 10^{-2} M$) in acetic anhydride for method M_2 , *N*-bromosuccinimide (0.088% or $4.94 \times 10^{-3} M$), acetic

Scheme 4. The formation of colored complex (well known as Ferrioin) in this method is shown.

Four reagents 2,3-dichloro-5,6-dicyano-1,4-benzoquinone (M_1), citric acid-acetic anhydride (M_2), *N*-bromosuccinimide/metol-sulphanilamide (M_3) and iron(III)-1,10-phenanthroline (M_4) have been developed for the determination of clopidogrel in four proposed methods (M_1 , M_2 , M_3 and M_4). The λ_{max} and ϵ_{max} values of the colored species formed for clopidogrel in descending order are $M_2 > M_3 > M_4 > M_1$ and $M_4 > M_3 > M_1 > M_2$, respectively. The descending order of precision is $M_3 > M_1, M_2 > M_4$. The accuracy in these methods is within 1.5%. There is good agreement between the values obtained from the reference and proposed methods in the assay of pharmaceutical formulations. All the proposed

acid solution (5% w/v or $8.75 \times 10^{-1} M$), potassium bromide (0.5% , $4.2 \times 10^{-2} M$), metol (0.3% or $8.71 \times 10^{-3} M$), sulphanilamide (0.2% or $1.16 \times 10^{-2} M$) in distilled water for method M_3 . Iron(III) (0.054% or $3.32 \times 10^{-3} M$), phenanthroline solution (0.2% or $1.10 \times 10^{-2} M$), *o*-phosphoric acid ($2.0 \times 10^{-2} M$) in distilled water for method M_4 were prepared.

Preparation of standard drug solution :

One mg/mL stock solution of clopidogrel in aqueous medium is prepared by dissolving 100 mg of the drug initially in 10 mL of 0.1 *M* hydrochloric acid and making up to 100 mL with distilled water (for methods M_3 and M_4); 1 mg/mL stock solution is prepared by dissolving

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100 mg of CLO in 100 mL methanol (for methods M_1 and M_2). The stock solution is further diluted to obtain working standard solution of concentration 100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ (for methods M_1 and M_2) with methanol and 100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ (for methods M_3 and M_4) with distilled water.

Analysis of tablets :

Tablets powder equivalent to 100 mg of active ingredient is dissolved in the appropriate solvent and filtered if necessary, and the working solutions of these methods (M_1 - M_4) are prepared as under standard solution preparation. They are analyzed as under the procedures given for pure samples.

Recommended procedures :

Method M_1 : Aliquots of standard drug solution (0.5–3.5 mL; 100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) are transferred into a series of 10 mL calibrated tubes and the volume in each tube was adjusted to 3.0 mL with dioxane. Then 1.0 mL of dimethyl formamide and 1 mL of DDQ solution were added and the total volume in each tube was adjusted to 10 mL with dioxane. The absorbances of the colored species were measured at 450 nm against a reagent blank during the stability period (immediate to 40 min). The amount of the drug present was calculated from the Beer-Lambert's plot. Beer's law obeyed in the concentration range of 5–35 $\mu\text{g/mL}$.

Method M_2 : Aliquots of standard drug solution (1.0–4.0 mL; 100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) were taken into a series of 25 mL graduated tubes and gently evaporated on a boiling water bath to dryness. To this, 10 mL of citric acid-acetic anhydride reagent was added and the flasks were immersed in a boiling water bath for 30 min. The tubes were cooled to room temperature and made up to 25 mL with acetic anhydride. The absorbances of the colored solutions were measured after 15 min at 560 nm against reagent blank. The drug concentration was computed from the calibration curve. Beer's law obeyed in the concentration range of 10–20 $\mu\text{g/mL}$.

Method M_3 : Aliquots of the standard drug solution (1.0–4.0 mL; 100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) were transferred into a series of 25 mL calibrated tubes containing 1.0 mL of acetic acid ($8.74 \times 10^{-1} M$), 0.5 mL of potassium bromide ($4.2 \times 10^{-2} M$), and 1.0 mL of *N*-bromosuccinimide ($4.9 \times 10^{-3} M$) solutions. The volume was brought to 10 mL with distilled water. The tubes were kept aside for 15

min at room temperature. Then 1.0 mL of $8.71 \times 10^{-3} M$ metol solution and after 2 min 2.0 mL of $1.16 \times 10^{-2} M$ sulphanilamide solution was added. The volume was made up to 25 mL with distilled water and the absorbance was measured after 10 min at 520 nm against distilled water. A blank experiment was also performed omitting drug solution. The decrease in absorbance corresponding to drug was obtained by subtracting the absorbance of test solution from that of the blank solution. The amount of drug present was calculated from its calibration graph. Beer's law obeyed in the concentration range of 4–16 $\mu\text{g/mL}$.

Method M_4 : Aliquots of standard drug solution ranging from 1.0–5.0 mL (100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) were transferred into a series of 10.0 mL volumetric flasks. To each flask 0.5 mL of aqueous solution of ferric chloride (0.05%) and 0.5 mL of methanolic solution of 1,10-phenanthroline (0.3% w/v) were added, heated on a water bath for 25 min and then cooled to room temperature. The final volume was made up to 10.0 mL with distilled water. The absorbance of the orange-red colored species formed was measured at 510 nm against the reagent blank. The absorbance of reaction product at 510 nm remained stable for 1 h. The amount of drug in the sample solution was computed from calibration curve. Beer's law obeyed in the concentration range of 10–50 $\mu\text{g/mL}$.

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